

Creating datasets of moth morphology and behaviour from textual sources with large language models

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Abstract. The integration of language models into ecological workflows is opening new possibilities for automated species monitoring. Classification systems are especially relevant in this context, as the high volume of data generated by automated systems requires efficient tools to support expert curators. Multimodal approaches, which incorporate textual information alongside visual or acoustic data, have shown potential to improve classification performance and interpretability. However, for many insect taxa, structured and usable textual descriptions remain scarce or difficult to access. In this work, we present a tool for retrieving and merging textual information about moth species from official repositories and citable sources. The resulting descriptions can be used to enrich multimodal classification models across different taxonomic levels or to build structured databases for species comparison and discovery.

Keywords: Computational Entomology · Automated insect monitoring · Multimodal category discovery · Large Language Models · Biodiversity.

1 Introduction

In recent years, there has been significant growth in the development of automated insect monitoring systems [10]. These technologies are made possible by recent advances in image-based machine learning models and low-power electronics, which together enable the construction of specialised devices designed specifically for this task [13]. This trend reflects the growing need to understand the dynamics of insect populations and how they are being affected by multiple environmental factors, including climate change [31], as most studies suggest a declining on populations has been a clear pattern each year (see [5] for specific UK data across multiple years and [31] for overall discussion).

Camera-based automated systems for monitoring insects have proven to be highly effective in generating large volumes of insect monitoring data, which has

in turn sparked a wide range of questions and applications in the field of computer science [11] [14] [25]. These range from how we collect and store ecological data to how we design robust algorithms for species classification or detecting rare species within datasets.

The vast amount of data collected by such systems presents a considerable workload in terms of identifying the species in each image. This highlights the urgent need for machine learning tools that can alleviate the burden on taxonomists — experts who are already in short supply [15] — by identifying species where the model is able, and referring others that require expert attention.

In this context, classification systems play a crucial role in helping us to make sense of complex datasets. Among these, multimodal systems are particularly promising, as they enable the integration of multiple types of data, such as text and images, within a shared feature space. This not only facilitates the interpretation of machine decisions but also supports clustering and labelling processes, even when the exact taxonomic classification of a specimen is unknown.

Deploying multimodal classification systems in entomology requires the creation of high-quality multimodal datasets — a task that presents unique challenges. Despite the availability of trait and abundance data, textual descriptions of insects —covering features such as colour, shape, and size — remain scarce, fragmented, and complex to process automatically. This contrasts with domains such as ornithology, where rich textual data resources are already available [20]. In addition to the value of trait data for supporting multimodal classification models, trait data are also crucial for understanding the role of species in ecological systems. The notable lack of trait data for insects is highlighted [16] [32].

In this work, we present our experience building a pipeline that leverages large language models (LLMs) to guide the extraction, standardisation, and formatting of species descriptions into usable forms for moth species. This contribution closes the gap between the potential of computational methods and the current limitations of available entomological data.

This paper is structured as follows: After the Introduction, Section 2 provides an overview of related work from a computational perspective, highlighting how textual information can support multimodal approaches in tasks such as classification and novel category discovery. In Section 3, we present our work on UK moths. Some experiments derived from the created dataset are given in Section 4, along with a brief discussion. Finally, we conclude the paper in Section 5 by reflecting on the outcomes of our work and outlining the next steps.

2 Related works

Image classification models continue to advance rapidly, with increasing capabilities being integrated into everyday applications. These models have recently been enhanced by the development of new multimodal architectures—a branch of machine learning that enables the joint representation of visual and textual data within a shared latent space. This shared space not only facilitates explain-

ability but also supports cross-modal applications, such as image-to-text and text-to-image generation [9].

One of the most widely used models in this area is CLIP [23], which employs a contrastive learning framework. In this architecture, the model learns to align images and their corresponding textual descriptions by bringing similar pairs closer in the latent space and pushing dissimilar ones apart. This approach has led to significant improvements, particularly in the task of novel category discovery [28,30], where the goal is to identify previously unseen categories in an open-world setting. This discovery-type scenario has clear implications in ecology, although it is not widely known and therefore not integrated into the automatic insect monitoring studies.

A multimodal perspective offers several advantages: it enables more targeted and guided training, improves generalisation, and enhances the interpretability of resulting clusters. While CLIP includes a relatively small text transformer by default, longer and more informative descriptions can be utilised through extensions such as LongCLIP [34], which is better suited to handling detailed textual data. In addition, there are now CLIP models trained on natural data as BIOCLIP [27] and InsectFoundation [29] that have shown the considerable potential these models have in the taxonomic / nature domain, creating a good starting point for fine-tuning tasks and other modalities alignment [33]. The trade-off, however, is that these models require a reliable source of textual descriptions corresponding to the images, so that a rich semantic latent space can be learned—linking the words used to describe insects with their visual representations. While such descriptions often exist in the form of trait annotations and identification keys, they are rarely available in structured datasets suitable for machine learning. Nevertheless, they represent a valuable resource in their own right, enabling applications such as natural language search and classification. One example is shown in [21], which presents a natural language classifier for insects based on Spanish descriptions. This problem becomes even more pronounced in biodiversity hotspots, such as Costa Rica. For this reason, studies like the present one contribute by proposing methods to generate and curate such datasets, serving as a foundation for the development of more accurate and practically useful multimodal resources.

3 Methodology

Our workflow is designed to extract, normalise, and synthesise textual descriptions of moth species from various online sources, supporting multimodal classification and structured trait extraction. The process involves several steps described below. A summary is presented in Figure 1. We began with a specific list of species based on a particular location (in this case, the United Kingdom), primarily to test our approach with a scenario that should contain a reasonable amount of textual descriptions and be well-documented. Based on that, we searched for databases of descriptions for UK and northern European species, as the overlap between those could offer a good complement. This is a key step that

may vary between different countries and is also the main challenge to overcome, as we will discuss in Section 5.

Fig. 1. Overview of the proposed workflow for textual data extraction, processing, and trait structuring.

3.1 Selection of Web Sources

We identified six web-based sources containing textual information about moth species/families/genus descriptions. These services include both official repositories and citable biodiversity platforms. The selected sources are:

- **Wikipedia** [4]: Wikipedia is a widely accessible and citable source that contains a substantial amount of biological information. It offers broad taxonomic coverage and is often the first point of reference for many users. However, its content is contributed by volunteers, and thus, the accuracy of descriptions can vary. While many pages do include cited references, there is a clear bias toward more popular or well-known species. Moreover, the textual information on species pages is typically unstructured, making it difficult to extract relevant data in a consistent manner. At higher taxonomic levels (e.g., genus or family), Wikipedia provides a high number of positives in terms of species coverage. However, the quality of this information tends to be low, as these pages often consist of long enumerations of species names without any accompanying morphological or behavioural descriptions.
- **Butterflies and Moths of North America** [2]: BAMONA is a curated online resource providing species information, distribution data, and user-submitted observations of Lepidoptera across North America. One of its strengths is the availability of concise species-level descriptions, often accompanied by high-quality images and confirmed locality records. Additionally, when species-level descriptions are not available, it is often possible to retrieve general information at the genus or family level. The data is curated

by several volunteers mentioned in the acknowledgements [1], and some of the identification keys come from three specific manuals that need to be cited [7] [3] [22]

- **UKMoths** [12]: UKMoths is a reference website for moths in the United Kingdom. It provides species profiles that include a variety of information such as life cycle, host plants, and physical appearance. However, the content is unstructured and not all entries contain the same fields, making text processing essential for extracting relevant data.
- **Animal Diversity** [17]: Animal Diversity offers species-level content with structured sections including descriptions and various biological data. Since much of the content is created by students, it is not always curated by domain experts. The platform is maintained by volunteers and is based in the USA, which introduces both geographical and popularity-related biases. Nevertheless, for species with complete entries, the site offers a wealth of well-organised information.
- **Swedish Museum of Natural History (NRM)** [6]: The NRM provides a repository containing textual and specimen-level information for species housed in the museum’s collections. For some species, general descriptive information is also available. We discovered this resource by following citation links from other biodiversity and abundance databases, where records of these specimens are maintained. There is an obvious geographic bias, but it has an insightful description of a wide selection of species.
- **Artfakta – SLU: Swedish Species Information Centre** [26]: Artfakta is another Swedish biodiversity repository frequently referenced in Scandinavian specimen abundance databases. The platform offers robust services and provides an API through which textual information, primarily written in Swedish, can be accessed. This facilitates automated extraction, and since experts curate the content, it is well-structured and organised. When descriptive text is available, it is typically easy to locate.

In summary, the selected sources, despite their value, obviously exhibit biases such as uneven geographic coverage, with underrepresentation of species outside the UK, North America, and Scandinavia. Some rely on user- or student-generated content, leading to inconsistencies in taxonomy or descriptive detail. When multiple descriptions exist, minor discrepancies (e.g., in colour or size) may arise; in such cases, our summarisation favours the more structured source. To ensure transparency, the dataset includes all original texts used, enabling verification. These limitations are further discussed in Section 5, and we advise verifying content before using descriptions for model training or trait analysis.

3.2 LLM-Guided Summarization

In this section, we explain our pipeline step by step, highlighting the key aspects of each step. A diagram of this is shown in Figure 2 for a specific species.

1. **Grouping and Translation** The collected texts are grouped by species, genus, or family to facilitate subsequent processing. Descriptions written

in languages other than English are translated using a machine translation system⁴ that is based on the DeepTranslator Python library⁵.

2. Merging

The translated descriptions are merged and cleaned to remove formatted content (such as species lists, which are commonly found in Wikipedia) and special characters. From webpages that have a fixed schema, description fields are extracted. For those which do not have it, regular expressions are used to search for the most similar header to the description. This step ensures that most irrelevant information is discarded for subsequent summarisation, reducing the text size.

3. Summarisation

We employ a LLM with tailored prompts (see source code 5 for a full description of the prompts used⁶) to generate three types of descriptions:

- **Morphological description:** covering antennae, body structure, colouration, and other visual features.
- **Behavioural description:** including months of activity, larval behaviour, and host plant preferences.
- **Visual-only morphological description:** a refined version of the morphological description, restricted to strictly visual traits, intended for use in downstream multimodal models.

The model is guided by structured prompts that were carefully designed depending on the type of summarisation task—morphological, behavioural, or visual-only. Each prompt included: (i) a specific framing or role context for the model (e.g., "You are an entomologist writing short scientific summaries"), (ii) a list of target traits or guide words (e.g., wingspan, forewings, antennae, colouration, host plants, flight period), and (iii) concrete examples of input-output pairs illustrating the expected format and content.

Importantly, the prompts were explicitly crafted to discourage hallucination and ensure that the output remains grounded in the available source information. This was achieved by instructing the model to state when information was unavailable or insufficient (e.g., returning "Sorry, information missing" or similar variants). This behaviour proved particularly useful when processing rare or poorly documented species, for which textual sources were incomplete or highly variable. These cases were primarily observed when applying the pipeline to the full dataset, where particular species yielded short or empty summaries, which were straightforward to detect and filter during post-processing.

To test performance, we implemented the summarisation pipeline using two large language models, including *gpt4-o-mini* [19,18] and LLaMA 3 [8]. We used LLaMA 3 via the Hugging Face Transformers pipeline. All generations

⁴ We avoided using LLMs for translation due to inconsistent performance on technical entomological vocabulary, though they remain a possible alternative.

⁵ <https://github.com/nidhaloff/deep-translator>

⁶ Latest updated prompts applied in our research can be found in a specific txt file in the *code* directory

were performed with the following parameters: *do sample* set to *False* (i.e., deterministic decoding), *max new tokens* set to 512. OpenAI models used the following generation parameters: *temperature=1.0*, *top_p=1.0*, *max_tokens* set by default (up to the model’s context limit), and both *frequency_penalty* and *presence_penalty* set to *0.0*. Due to its smaller size and the lack of sampling, LLaMA 3 exhibited lower performance in our summarisation task compared to *gpt4-o-mini*. Therefore, subsequent analysis will primarily focus on results from *gpt4-o-mini*.

To verify the factual accuracy of the generated summaries, we applied the *faithfulness* metric from the RAGAS evaluation framework⁷. This metric estimates how well the generated text is grounded in the provided sources by using a reference LLM (in this case, *GPT4-o* [19,18]), larger than the one used in the summarisation, to check whether each factual statement in the summary can be traced back to the source material. This serves as an initial, indicative metric that helps confirm the system is not introducing hallucinations or noise, and that it remains faithful to the original content. Nevertheless, human expert validation would still be necessary to cross-check that there are no errors in the original sources.

The full implementation of the summarisation process with each model, along with the evaluation results of each step and examples, are available in the public repository.

4. Dual Textual Datasets

The output of the LLM is assembled into a dataset containing cleaned and standardised descriptions per species, one for the morphological traits and the other for the behavioural characteristics (more broadly, including larval behaviour, eating patterns, and months). The result is a dataset that could be suitable for training multimodal classification systems or conducting ecological trait analysis via unsupervised trait extraction from the data, an example of this can be seen in Section 4.

5. Structured Trait Extraction

In a final step, we optionally guide the LLM to transform the descriptive data into structured tables capturing individual traits (e.g., wing span, colouration patterns, activity periods). This structured dataset enables several downstream applications, such as:

- Trait-based species comparison;
- Integration with existing ecological trait databases;
- Semi-automated validation of extracted descriptions through comparison with known trait values.

This dual use—as both a reference and a validation tool—enhances the robustness of the overall workflow and facilitates its integration into ecological monitoring pipelines. One example of this application could utilise models trained in works like [21] with descriptions, along with vision models via contrastive learning, as in [33]. This model enabled natural language search within a set of pictures and zero-shot, few-shot classification of images, which can be potentially helpful in discovering novel categories.

⁷ <https://docs.ragas.io/en/latest/>

3.3 Description Generation

We could complement textual sources with a visual approach using a pipeline that crops moth specimens from iNaturalist images. These can be processed by multimodal large language models (MLLMs), such as LLaVA and GPT-4-V, to generate captions emphasising traits like colouration, wing shape, and other morphological features.

This method could be useful when textual data is scarce, such as in hyper-diverse ecosystems or museum collections lacking detailed annotations, but it still needs to learn from the datasets that combine both images and texts, as the one we are creating here.

Fig. 2. Example of the pipeline for *Adela croesella*.

4 Results

In this section, we present the first results of our approach from the UK dataset. First, we will describe the species coverage that can be obtained from the dataset. We start with a dataset that contains 2682 species from 213 genus and 57 families of moths, with a variable length and distribution (see Table 1 and Figure 3 for additional details). This species list was extracted from the master list used in the AMI project for automatic moth monitoring⁸. It comprises moth species recorded and counted in GBIF for the United Kingdom for which we have photographic records, making them suitable for automatic visual recognition. The

⁸ <https://github.com/AMI-system>

genus and family information is derived directly from these species, and the released dataset includes the scientific name, common name, and the *GBIF taxon ID*⁹ to link these names with any other nomenclature used in the sources or by other databases.

This coverage can be generalised to some extent to other northern regions, as many of the same resources and species overlap; therefore, we expect a comparable number of descriptions to be obtainable for those areas as well. In the results, we present insights into the species coverage and demonstrate how textual models can be applied to the morphological descriptions for tasks such as similarity search. We discuss both aspects further after the results are presented. Section 5 will outline the next steps based on the data presented here.

4.1 Species Coverage

To assess the quality and richness of the generated morphological and behavioural descriptions, we computed basic statistics across three taxonomic levels: species, genus and family. These statistics include the average number of words, standard deviation, the number of descriptions with fewer than 20 words, and the corresponding percentage. Table 1 summarises the results. In terms of coverage, based on GBIF records¹⁰, we achieved morphological descriptions longer than 20 words for 79.9% of species and behavioural descriptions longer than 20 words for 89.7%. The average coverage across families is 84.8% for morphological descriptions and 92.6% for behavioural ones. Notably, the families *Tortricidae* (only 62% morphology, 89% behaviour) and *Noctuidae* (only 85% morphology, 85% behaviour) show the largest absolute gaps in the number of species not yet described in the dataset.

Table 1. Descriptive statistics of morphological and behavioural descriptions across taxonomic levels.

Level	Type	Mean	Std.	Less than 20 words
Species	Morphological	57.56	38.47	19.35%
	Behavioral	42.36	18.55	9.26%
Family	Morphological	42.82	25.78	24.56%
	Behavioral	48.75	27.07	15.79%
Genus	Morphological	48.72	30.08	14.55%
	Behavioral	36.40	19.38	21.60%

Overall, morphological descriptions tend to be longer than behavioural ones across all taxonomic levels. The species-level descriptions exhibit the highest average word count for morphology, while the genus-level behavioural descriptions show the highest proportion of short texts (less than 20 words).

⁹ <https://www.gbif.org/dataset/d7dddbf4-2cf0-4f39-9b2a-bb099caae36c>

¹⁰ <https://doi.org/10.15468/dl.b9nhv6>

Fig. 3. Histogram of descriptions lengths for species, genus and families from the UK dataset.

4.2 Textual similarity

In addition to descriptive statistics, we evaluated the semantic similarity among the morphological and behavioural descriptions using a pretrained language model. Specifically, we employed the *all-MiniLM-L6-v2*¹¹ model from the *sentence-transformers* library [24], which provides a lightweight transformer-based architecture for computing sentence embeddings.

Each description was embedded into a high-dimensional semantic space, and cosine similarity was used to measure pairwise similarities between descriptions within the species range. Results showed that morphological descriptions exhibit a similarity $mean = 0.6147$, $std = 0.1271$, while behaviour similarity $mean = 0.6258$ with $std = 0.125$. Some examples are shown in Figure 4, where a random species was selected and its similarity to all other species was computed. We then selected the top 3 most similar, the bottom 3 least similar, and 3 examples with mid-range similarity.

4.3 Results’ discussions

It is important to note that this analysis was conducted using a pretrained language model that was not specifically trained on insect-related descriptions. Therefore, this represents only a preliminary exploration of how general-purpose language models interpret and compare the semantic content of these descriptions.

From the results, we observe that species with similar description structures tend to be marked as highly similar. For instance, the top three most similar descriptions often follow a standard descriptive scheme, highlighting comparable traits such as metallic colouration, head patterning, or wing texture. In contrast, the least similar descriptions are often brief and lack detail; they frequently refer to general information, such as size or resemblance to other species, without elaborating on specific morphological features. This hypothesis was tested by comparing morphological descriptions in short texts (less than 20

¹¹ <https://huggingface.co/sentence-transformers/all-MiniLM-L6-v2>

words), which exhibited a significantly lower mean similarity to other descriptions ($\mu_{short} = 0.5286$) compared to longer ones ($\mu_{long} = 0.6309$). A similar pattern was observed for behavioural descriptions, where short texts averaged $\mu_{short} = 0.4923$ in similarity versus $\mu_{long} = 0.6340$ for long ones. These differences were statistically significant, as shown by the results of independent t-tests: Morphological descriptions: $t = -20.19, p < 0.05$ and Behavioral descriptions: $t = -11.98, p < 0.05$.

These findings suggest that shorter descriptions tend to be less semantically aligned with the rest of the dataset. This may be due to reduced lexical richness, a lack of detailed traits, or template-like phrasing, which limits their usefulness in tasks that require semantic comparison.

Descriptions with mid-range similarity are typically more detailed and offer a more nuanced comparison. While not identical in content, they tend to share semantically rich elements, such as references to colours and textures commonly used in moth descriptions, which result in moderate similarity scores. These findings suggest that semantic similarity scores can reflect both structural and content-based resemblance, particularly when the descriptions are sufficiently informative and detailed. These models will enhance their discriminative power when trained alongside images in multimodal approaches, or we could further fine-tune them for a specific classification task, for example. This will improve the model’s performance for those with complete descriptions, as well as for others that require further completion. At the same time, the question of a standardised or at least similar description pattern arises, and that’s an interesting application of a structured trait/descriptive database, from which we can create those.

Fig. 4. Similarity matrix from Adela croesella selecting top three, mid three and bottom three matching descriptions. Some photos of the species are highlighted in green (top 3), orange (mid-similarity), and red (low-similarity).

As part of this work, we publish an open partial dataset comprising the 100 most common moth species in the UK, selected based on occurrence data from iNaturalist in the United Kingdom, along with family and genus. This dataset includes the original textual sources used for summarisation, allowing for detailed evaluation and reproducibility. The *faithfulness* metric was applied to this subset as a preliminary indicator of its validation and standardisation. These scores provide insight into the alignment between generated summaries and their source materials, serving as a first step toward ensuring data reliability in downstream applications. The average *faithfulness* score for morphological descriptions was 0.956 ($\sigma = 0.112$), while behavioural descriptions scored slightly higher, with a mean of 0.978 ($\sigma = 0.081$). These values suggest a strong factual alignment between the generated summaries and their corresponding source texts, supporting the reliability of the summarisation pipeline in preserving original content. We detected some differences between descriptions, as well as additional descriptions (pages where moths and larvae are described simultaneously) in cases where faithfulness was below 1.0, highlighting this approach as a first step in analysing the initial data. The Families dataset also showed similar performance, whereas the Genus dataset was the only one with notably lower scores. Upon analysis, these lower scores were attributed to the model providing characteristics of specific species within the genus, likely because most of the source materials consisted of species lists. This remains the only detected example of hallucination in the model.

5 Conclusions and future works

The workflow presented in this work demonstrates a comprehensive pipeline that can retrieve data from textual sources and summarise it in a manner that is beneficial for multimodal approaches, as well as the creation of new resources (both structured and unstructured). One of the main aspects that is still an open issue is the validation of the final data. At any point in the pipeline, the descriptions remain perfectly traceable from the sources, allowing for any check to be made to assess the summarisation performance. Additionally, the trait database can also serve as a double-check system, where previously known traits are cross-referenced with extracted ones to verify accuracy. Another relevant issue we detected using the similarity approach is the need for a standardised and structured collection of descriptions, as length and content may affect the similarities.

A significant challenge is the lack of accessible, digitised taxonomic records. Outside Europe, structured species descriptions are scarce and often trapped in non-digital or paywalled formats. Even in the UK, unified collections of morphological or behavioural text data are limited. Historically, text descriptions were not considered machine-readable, but this is changing: digitalisation and semantic structuring now enable both the extraction and generation of coherent taxonomic descriptions.

Crucially, biodiversity monitoring and taxonomy remain deeply tied to domain expertise. While AI can assist and accelerate specific tasks, it must not overshadow the core issue: the chronic underfunding and fragmentation of taxonomic knowledge. Any models developed from this data should remain open, shareable, and built in close collaboration with entomologists and taxonomists.

Future work will involve expanding the current approach to incorporate more structured data and taxonomic nomenclature, particularly from under-represented regions. We also plan to benchmark multimodal models against fine-tuned models with this data to assess their performance across ecological contexts (images vs text vs images + text). Ultimately, our goal is to develop adaptable, lightweight tools that serve entomologists and strengthen computational support for biodiversity conservation.

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Source code Source code, prompts and other supplementary material can be found at <https://theboort.github.io/ecodl2025-paper/>

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